

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE COMPETENCIES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE PIANO)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11280403>

Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the methodology of piano performance in the development of musical instrument performance competencies in music education students of the higher pedagogical education system.

Key words: Musical education, piano, instrument performance, commentary, textbook, choir, methodological training.

Introduction.

Looking at the process of teaching a musical instrument as a separate activity based on specific educational tasks, it can be said that the main focus here is to form students' creative abilities, to teach them to understand and feel the beauty in art, to be a special name in the culture and art of Uzbek and neighboring nations it is necessary to introduce the works of world nations and composers.

In our conversations with pedagogues working in this direction, we were convinced that it is enough to teach students how to play an instrument at an amateur level, learn music independently by the notes of any piece, analyze and read from a sheet. It is necessary to teach. Future teachers must listen to music carefully, analyze it theoretically, and have the skills to learn by reading from a sheet.

We studied the works of many musician-pedagogues and scientists who researched the content of musical performance in the "musical education" specialty of the higher pedagogical education system. Forming worldview, moral, spiritual, intellectual, cocktail, and physical education by means of music has its own characteristics.¹ Summarizing all their leading psychological-pedagogical and musicological concepts, based on their analysis, we selected the following components to determine the content of musical performance:

- *musical aesthetic knowledge;*
- *performance skills;*
- *practical engagement with music;*
- *analysis and aesthetic assessment of musical works;*

¹ Oodirov R. "Musiqqa pedagogikasi" 2005 yil, 31 b.

- *performance and oral interpretation of musical works and jazz music;*
- *creative experience in creating, aesthetic to music and musical activity.*

It would be appropriate to say that we got the experience of attitude.

While the main task of the musical instrument class is to teach students how to play an instrument, the activities of students cannot be limited to performance. In our opinion, in this regard, the goal of encouraging students to learn musical instruments, to play tunes of various genres, forms and styles, to read from a sheet, to play in an ensemble, to acquire technical skills based on learning exercises and etudes puts.²

Musical performance in the process of learning a musical instrument gathers various types of activities around the main repertoire of the student and connects them with the studied works.

For reading music from a sheet and listening (performed by a teacher and by listening with the help of technical devices), works with the main performance repertoire of the student are selected according to genre and style. Tasks related to the analysis of the figurative content, compositional structure and musical expressiveness of the works are focused on the search for the artistic quality of the performance (dynamics, articulation, nuances, performance techniques) and performance styles.

Elements of creative music training (playing what you hear, sounds transfer, arrangement, accompaniment, etc.) performance of the student. It is appropriate if it is performed depending on the repertoire and the amount of musical theoretical knowledge.

Reading music from a page, creating a piece, listening and aesthetic evaluation The consistency of educational assignments and tasks, which are increasingly simple from simple to complex, creates a system of various musical activities that summarizes the knowledge, skills and abilities students have acquired in the process of learning music.

According to teachers with many years of experience, it is not enough for future music teachers to learn the sound of an instrument perfectly. For this reason, it is useful to inform students about each musical instrument, their characteristics, and the methods and ways of making the melodies performed with them. For example, a creative approach to the education of students learning to play the piano ensures the connection of music education and training with musical practice, and clarifies the aesthetic and ideological-ethical tasks of musical education.

² Ройтерштейн И.М. “Книга о музыке” Sankt-Peterburg.: 2014 y., 45 b.

Individually, according to the pedagogical classification of piano lessons, the skills of playing in an ensemble and being an accompanist are included in educational activities, the skills of practical engagement with music (listening, copying sounds, reading from a sheet) are included in independent educational activities, the analysis and aesthetic evaluation of musical works skills can be divided into skills of mental activity. It is pedagogically correct to define the requirements for mastering these parts of piano lessons by students in each course section. The most convenient and effective form of piano training is solo is a form of order. It has a number of advantages, including: enables close contact and relationship with students, learns students' personal capabilities, individual characteristics closely, assigns assignments accordingly, corrects shortcomings, creates a favorable environment for development, provides a deep understanding of the student's personality.

The teacher should pay special attention to two aspects.

- implementation of specific knowledge, skills and qualifications at a certain stage;
- to consider it as an important part of the implementation of long-term tasks.

Students should be given specific tasks in each lesson. For example, theoretical concepts, strengthening the work, working on performance techniques, elements of metrorhythm or technical performance, etc.

Achieving consistency of training, in which the knowledge gained in one lesson it is necessary to strengthen skills and competencies in the next training.

Learn the material gradually, step by step, simply it is necessary to develop according to the norm of new knowledge based on the principle of complexity.

Tasks are completed with the help of the teacher-supervisor, under his control, and later on his own

By doing it, the student can develop the ability to work independently. Independent study of easy, simple works, performing them at various events or during the test has an effective effect on the development of independent work skills in the student. Conducting most of the lessons in an integrated form, i.e. checking homework, giving an understanding of a new piece, showing it in practice, giving theoretical concepts, reading from a sheet, copying sounds, playing in an ensemble, etc. leads to increase.³ The future music teacher should not forget that the quality and content of the lessons largely depends on the teacher's preparation. The teacher should prepare separately for each lesson,

³ Muhammedova Z. "Fortepiano chalishni o'rgatish uslubiyoti" Toshkent.: 2006 y., 16 b.

plan the project of the lesson with the student in advance, take into account the necessary components for his creative development, and the most important thing is to systematically train the children, taking into account their musical abilities. must be carried out in connection with the tasks of development, it must be in his constant attention that no success can be achieved without developing musical abilities, in particular, musical perception.

Various forms of training can be used appropriately. This instead, the mixed type of the lesson includes reading the performed repertoire from a sheet, playing in an ensemble, independent self-work, etc.

Group-individual lessons are accompanied by a group of students, listening to music will make the ensemble more active.

Conducting such lessons before certain events (concert, audition, test) has a positive effect on increasing students' sense of responsibility.

Independent work in the lesson is a unique form of training students work on the development of a piece of music, a part of it, or specific goal-oriented features with the participation of a teacher-leader. What mistakes did the student make in this, the tasks of solving difficulties, the issues of what should be paid more attention are resolved.

Knowledge, abilities, skills of students in some or complete circle and speaking about the formation and development of skills, it should not be forgotten that the exercises in the piano class depend on the interesting, free and varied repertoire. Here are the practical ways to successfully solve these tasks.

1. When working with students of different interest and abilities taking into account their individual characteristics, assigning specific tasks to each of them.

2. To work on various performance tasks, to increase the number of works to be studied, to include examples of various complexity in the repertoire of each student.

3. From the pieces specially written for the piano during the educational process, selected exercises, reworked folk songs in addition to etudes, reworked and simplified music written in the academic style and genre, later (at later stages of education) pieces of opera, ballet, reworked works for 4, 6, 8 hands piano ensemble , samples written specifically for piano ensemble can be included.

Cultivating musical interest and abilities is a comprehensive pedagogy it is necessary to solve the tasks correctly from the point of view of education and upbringing, to set serious performance tasks based on the materials suitable for the students' capabilities. It is pedagogical to try to remember as many

previously studied works as possible in order to strengthen the achieved results ensures efficient operation

References:

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